

Microave dielectric relaxation spectroscopy studies on polar –polar binary liquid mixtures of triethylene glycol with ethyl butyrate.

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Abstract

The complex dielectric spectra of triethylene glycol with ethyl butyrate and their binary mixtures were measured in the frequency range of 10 MHz to 50 GHz at various temperatures using Time Domain Reflectometric (TDR) technique. The dielectric parameters (static permittivity and relaxation time) were extracted from the complex permittivity spectra by using least square fit method. Debye relaxation model is suitable for extracting the dielectric parameters. The derived static permittivity (ϵ') and relaxation time (τ) values were used to calculate various dielectric parameters like excess dielectric constant, effective Kirkwood correlation factor, excess inverse relaxation time and thermodynamic parameters. Excess dielectric parameters were fitted with the Redlich–Kister type polynomial equation. The result of dielectric relaxation studies confirms the formation of a heterogeneous complex structure by association of unlike molecules and may also intra molecular interaction possible between similar molecules. Molecular rotation and dipole reorientation motions in these complex systems are discussed in terms of the molar activation entropy and enthalpy. Additionally, the hydrogen bond interaction between solute and solvent were confirmed by FT–IR spectral analysis.

Keywords: Complex permittivity, dielectric constant, molecular interaction, Effective dipole, enthalphy.

References

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